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A NEW KISSING NUMBER OF THE REGULAR POLYGON

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ABSTRACT. Let P_n be an arbitrary regular polygon with n sides. The kissing number $k(P_n)$ is the maximum number of congruent regular polygons (copies of P_n) that can be arranged so that each touches P_n but no two of them overlap. Youngs (1939), Klamkin (1995), Zhao (1998, 2002) and others established that $k(P_3) = 12$, $k(P_4) = 8$ and $k(P_n) = 6$ with $n \geq 5$. In this paper, we will study a new kissing number. Let Q_n be a regular polygon with n sides whose length of side is the half of P_n . What is the maximum number $k_1(P_n)$ of congruent regular polygons Q_n that can be arranged so that each touches P_n but no two of them overlap? We will prove that $k_1(P_n) = 9$ when $n \geq 9$.

1. Introduction

Two plane figures are said to kiss each other if they do not overlap but their boundaries have nonempty intersection. For a plane figure F , a kissing configuration of order n consists of $n + 1$ congruent nonoverlapping copies of F such that one copy kisses each of the remaining n . The kissing number of F , denoted by $k(F)$, is the largest integer n such that a kissing configuration of order n exists for F .

Let P_n be an arbitrary regular polygon with n sides. For the square P_4 , Youngs ([1]) seems to have been the first to establish that $k(P_3) = 12$ and $k(P_4) = 8$. The determination of $k(P_4)$ was later posed as a Putnam competition problem. Youngs' result was reproduced in the solution book ([3]). Klamkin et al. ([2]) also gave an elementary proof that $k(P_4) = 8$ and presented a few kissing configurations of order $k(P_6) = 6$ for P_6 . Zhao et al. ([5,6]) established that $k(P_n) = 6$ with $n \geq 5$.

In this paper, we will study a new kissing number. Let Q_n be a regular polygon with n sides whose length of side is the half of P_n . What is the maximum number $k_1(P_n)$ of congruent regular polygons Q_n that can be arranged so that each touches P_n but no two of them overlap? We will prove that $k_1(P_n) = 9$ when $n \geq 9$.

2. Main result

Theorem 2.1. *Suppose that P_n is an arbitrary regular polygon with n sides and*

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$n \geq 9$. Then

$$k_1(P_n) = 9.$$

In order to prove the above Theorem, we first prove the following Lemmas.

Lemma 2.2. $k_1(P_n) \geq 9$.

Proof. Suppose that P is an circle with radius 2, it is easy to see that there are 9 circles with radius 1 around P which are tangent to it. Since any regular polygon with n sides have an circumcircle, so the proposition holds. \square

In the following, we always suppose that $n \geq 9$.

Lemma 2.3. Suppose that P_n is an arbitrary regular polygon with n sides. Let Q_n and Q'_n be two regular polygons with n sides whose length of side is the half of P_n . P_n kisses both Q_n and Q'_n such that Q_n and Q'_n kiss each other. Let O, A, B be the centers of P_n, Q_n and Q'_n respectively. Note $\angle AOB$ by θ_n . Then

$$\theta_n \geq \arccos \frac{8 - \cos \frac{2\pi}{n}}{9}.$$

Proof. Without loss of generality, we suppose that $R = 2$, then $r_n = 2\cos \frac{\pi}{n}$, where R is the radius of P_n , r_n is the distance from the center of P_n to its side. Then we have $R' = 1$ and $r'_n = \cos \frac{\pi}{n}$, where R' is the radius of Q_n and Q'_n , r'_n is the distance from the centers of Q_n and Q'_n to their sides. Clearly, both OA and OB are at least $r_n + r'_n = 3\cos \frac{\pi}{n}$ and at most $R + R' = 3$, and AB is at least $2r'_n = 2\cos \frac{\pi}{n}$.

Since $AB \geq 2r'_n = 2\cos \frac{\pi}{n}$, if we replace the triangle $\triangle AOB$ by the triangle $\triangle A_1OB_1$ with $OA_1 = OA$, $OB_1 = OB$, $A_1B_1 = 2\cos \frac{\pi}{n}$, then $\angle AOB \geq \angle A_1OB_1$. Let $OA_1 = x$ and $OB_1 = y$. By the Law of Cosines, we have

$$\cos \angle A_1OB_1 = (x^2 + y^2 - 4\cos^2 \frac{\pi}{n})/2xy,$$

where $3\cos \frac{\pi}{n} \leq x, y \leq 3$. Let $F(x, y) = \cos \angle A_1OB_1 = (x^2 + y^2 - 4\cos^2 \frac{\pi}{n})/2xy$, then

$$F'_x(x, y) = (x^2 - y^2 + 4\cos^2 \frac{\pi}{n})/2x^2y,$$

$$F'_y(x, y) = (y^2 - x^2 + 4\cos^2 \frac{\pi}{n})/2y^2x.$$

Since $n \geq 6$, then $\tan \frac{\pi}{n} \leq \tan \frac{\pi}{6} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{3} < \frac{2}{3}$. From $3\cos \frac{\pi}{n} \leq x, y \leq 3$, we have

$$x^2 - y^2 + 4\cos^2 \frac{\pi}{n} \geq (3\cos \frac{\pi}{n})^2 - 9 + 4\cos^2 \frac{\pi}{n} = 4\cos^2 \frac{\pi}{n} - 9\sin^2 \frac{\pi}{n} > 0.$$

This inequality implies that $F'_x(x, y) > 0$ and $F'_y(x, y) > 0$. Therefore,

$$F(x, y) \leq F(3, y) \leq F(3, 3) = 1 - \frac{2}{9}\cos^2 \frac{\pi}{n} = \frac{8 - \cos \frac{2\pi}{n}}{9}.$$

Now, the above relation implies that

$$\theta_n = \angle AOB \geq \angle A_1OB_1 = \arccos F(x, y) \geq \arccos F(3, 3) \geq \arccos\left[\frac{8 - \cos\frac{2\pi}{n}}{9}\right].$$

This completes the proof. \square

Proof. Proof of the Theorem 2.1 Let $\alpha_n = \arccos\left[\frac{8 - \cos\frac{2\pi}{n}}{9}\right]$, then $\theta_n \geq \alpha_n$. Let $\phi_n = \frac{360^\circ}{\theta_n}$. When $n = 9$, we have $\cos\frac{2\pi}{9} > 0.7660$, $\alpha_9 > 36.50^\circ$. So $\theta_9 > 36.50^\circ$. Thus

$$\phi_9 = \frac{360^\circ}{\theta_9} < \frac{360^\circ}{36.50^\circ} < 9.8631.$$

It follows that $k_1(P_9) \leq 9$.

When $n \geq 9$, $\cos\frac{2\pi}{n} < \cos\frac{2\pi}{n+1}$ implies

$$\arccos\frac{8 - \cos\frac{2\pi}{n}}{9} < \arccos\frac{8 - \cos\frac{2\pi}{n+1}}{9}.$$

It follows that $\phi_n > \phi_{n+1}$. When $n \geq 9$ we have

$$k_1(P_n) \leq k_1(P_9) \leq 9.$$

From Lemma 2.1 it follows that $k_1(P_n) = 9$ when $n \geq 9$.

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